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Specific Characteristics of Primary School Education and Development Prospects

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Abstract: *The scientific discipline of primary school education is closely related to the profession of primary school teacher. A systematic historical review of the development of the profession and discipline cannot and should not be undertaken, but attention should be paid to success stories as well as to persistent problem areas. Based on this, we will talk about primary school pedagogy and the specifics of the primary school teacher profession. Further development of the specificity of primary school pedagogy provides not only the opportunity to counter the looming threat of deprofessionalization through lateral access, but also the authority to claim expert knowledge and thus comment on the central current areas of discourse. This is done in the case of school inclusion. In contrast to the concept of special education represented by special education, the mainstream discourse of inclusive education emphasizes the need to define and theorize the specificity of primary school education as the future.*

Key words: *profession, special education, primary school, school inclusion, education, concept.*

Introduction

We know that primary school education plays a crucial role in the basic development of children. In the process of writing this small scientific study, we believe that there are some specific features and potential development prospects for this stage of education, and their application in the educational process will bring effective results. They are as follows. The first is called holistic development, which focuses on intellectual, emotional, social and physical development through a balanced curriculum¹. The next is developmental education, which emphasizes active learning, encouraging children to

¹ Ro'ziyeva D., Ismatova N. va boshqalar Darslik. 3-sinf darslik. Toshkent "SANOSTANDART" 2020

explore, ask questions, and engage in hands-on activities. The next, called social skills, is important because it focuses on developing basic literacy and numeracy skills, along with critical thinking and problem-solving skills. The next is called game-based learning, which includes a quality of life component, recognizing the importance of play in learning and cognitive development. The next, called individual differences, recognizes that children learn at different rates and in different ways, which calls for differentiated instruction. A so-called emphasis on socialization encourages cooperation and interaction among peers, encourages social skills and teamwork, and finally manifests itself as parent and community involvement, in which the It involves families and communities in the learning process and creates a supportive learning environment.

Here are some ways are given to think about the future of primary school education: 1. The Technology Integration phase involves increasing the use of digital tools and resources to enhance the learning experience and access to information. 2. The Curriculum Innovation phase initiates the development of more flexible and adaptable curricula that meet different learning needs and current societal demands. 3. Emotional Intelligence focuses on the growing importance of emotional and social learning alongside academic achievement. 4. Global Competence focuses on teaching children about global issues, cultural awareness, and the importance of cooperation in a globalized world. 5. Implementing Environmental Education to instill a sense of responsibility for green spaces during the Sustainable Education phase. 6. The Inclusive Education Practice phase aims to accommodate children from diverse backgrounds entering school, with a focus on ensuring equality in education. In the final phase, the goal is to cultivate an interest and love of learning that extends beyond primary education. These characteristics and perspectives reflect a dynamic approach to primary education that meets the needs of modern society while ensuring the overall growth of children.

Main part

The demand for a comprehensive theory of basic education also plays a central role in the controversial research on the self-assessment of primary school education as a scientific discipline, and the identification of primary school education with rationally structured education is associated with the possibility. A special issue that is required of today's researchers is that it is necessary not to consider the characteristics of primary school education independently of the objects of research and the quality of the research. At the moment, the above-mentioned demands seem more urgent than ever. We can see many research projects in primary schools that collect their empirical data, but sometimes we see that the research is carried out without reference to the theoretical foundations of primary school education and without considering their relevance for practice. From Kahlert's point of view, the focus on originality also has a reliable substantive value for innovative design processes in primary schools and their classrooms.

As for the specifics of the primary school teacher profession, it is based, in principle, on the same professional requirements as the secondary school teacher profession. The primary school initiative justifies the shift in emphasis to the scientific direction of teaching by the principle that there is no difference in nature and value between the learning processes at the beginning or at the end of the learning stages.

In the process of communication, students' behavior is distinguished and approached depending on the presence of a problem. Preparation for full-time teaching practice for primary and secondary school teachers always implies training at a scientific university. According to the legislation of developed countries, it is recognized that there should be no difference between scientific research and practical

training. It goes on to explain the commonality of tasks that are central to the training of all teachers in the field of education, psychology and social sciences.

Regardless of the educational legislation of any country in the world, the same training standards apply to all teaching professions in the field of education. The qualification requirements for areas of responsibility are the same for all types of teaching professions. School pedagogy and educational psychology also rarely provide theoretical and empirical knowledge that they generate at specific levels of school or teacher training. The corresponding professional theories based on the structural theory approach, the competence theory approach and the expert approach are also relevant to the teaching profession as a whole, even if they relate it to the actions of primary school teachers. In this regard, the general knowledge base of all teachers in the subjects of study is very large. Nevertheless, the profession of a primary school teacher also includes specific requirements for professional skills, which are subsequently fulfilled in connection with the requirements of the educational program and the requirements of the educational institution.

Primary school teachers work in primary schools. A school for all children, i.e. in which the students are largely not chosen and in which all children are potentially reached through inclusion. At the same time, primary school teachers have a special social responsibility for equality of opportunity, social integration and democracy. In order to do justice to the diverse student groups, they must balance the tension between social integration and individualization in all educational matters. Primary school teachers are responsible for the basic education of all children. They create the basis for further educational processes. Although the need for further theorization of basic education was emphasized at the beginning of this article, we will repeat below that, according to the researcher Einsiedler², the components of basic education are four characteristics:

1. Common basic education for all, 2. common foundation, 3. beginning of common education and 4. personality formation. Skills acquisition tasks are of particular interest in the areas of reading, writing, mathematics, and general education. They convey the "common foundation" of the educational goals of primary schools and the foundations of cultural acquisition with the basic skills necessary for independent learning. At this point, we can say that the scientific and didactic skills belonging to the primary school perform important tasks for the successful learning process of every child.

In the first grade of the school system, primary school teachers should form the ability to connect the individual tasks of students to primary and secondary levels. In this direction, special competencies are required for the stage of starting school, primary classes and formation of school qualifications. Since the establishment of the primary school, on the one hand, it has been a child-friendly, independent school, and on the other hand, it has had a dual function to achieve the expected result, especially with the supply function for the secondary school³. This also applies to the contrasting functions of support and selection, which are important in primary school teaching due to their high relevance for further education. Elementary school teachers should familiarize themselves with the conditions of growth related to the mental development and life world of especially young children, take them into account in all upbringing and education processes, and help to form them in every way.

² Einsiedler, W. (2011): Grundlegende Bildung. In: W. Einsiedler, M. Götz, A. Hartinger, F. Heinzl, J. Kahlert & U. Sandfuchs (Hrsg.): Handbuch Grundschulpädagogik und Grundschuldidaktik. 3. Aufl., Bad Heilbrunn: Klinkhardt, 211-218.

³ Hänsel, D. (1988): Die Grundschule: Zwischen pädagogischem Anspruch und gymnasialen Erwartungsdruck. In: Pädagogik 40 (3), 43-48.

In order to be able to respond to these specific requirements and characteristics, the role of the class leader in primary schools is of particular importance. The success stories of both the profession and the discipline are summarized in articles and research papers that constitute and define distinctive features. At the same time, high similarities were noted, for example, in terms of discipline with school pedagogy and professional similarities with all other teaching professions.

In this part of our article, we will think about the role and place of primary education as a leading concept for covering the school to the primary class. It is no exaggeration to say that until now, the profession and discipline of elementary school education have been in harmony with the leading concept of special education support and have complemented each other. The main goal of the development perspective is to adhere to educational programs that do not separate children from each other in the educational process, and at the same time, by confirming the basic educational requirements of the elementary school, education in the sense of the pedagogical discipline and professional responsibility of the elementary school. is to express the power of the reef in a more aggressive way. We can take the experience of developed countries as an example of such approaches.

Today, the discipline of primary school education corresponds to the guiding concept of basic education. In the previous section, Einsiedler's concept was outlined, which can be used as a basis for a broad understanding of uncompromising inclusion. The researchers Deckert-Piesmann, Seifert⁴ and Klafki⁵ describe basic education at the primary level as the beginning of general education and emphasize that it is far from the idea of minimum standards and basic skills. Therefore, the high significance of basic education for both the discipline and the profession was emphasized. Regardless of the further theorization of this term, it is already clear that it is based on a more comprehensive, general educational need than the understanding of education that dominates the tradition of secondary school education and the linear understanding of diagnosis, support and tireless work to achieve success in special education⁶. The concept of special educational needs, which is also reflected in the concept of support for special education, also refers to the "needs" of children, which are often defined by disabilities; and this requires a discriminating classification or grouping of children, but it was previously applied to primary school education with the concept of basic education. In the tradition of didactics of auxiliary schools, the reduced educational requirements still influence modern didactic concepts⁷.

Werning⁸ summarizes it as follows: "Less than usual, sharper than usual, steps smaller than usual, slower than usual, and stronger than usual."

When we looked at primary school education in developed countries, we found that in Germany there is some freedom in the accounting of primary school teachers⁹. Initially, primary school education

⁴ Deckert-Peacemann, H. & Seifert, A. (2019): Grundlegende Bildung. In: B. Dühlmeier & U. Sandfuchs (Hrsg.): 100 Jahre Grundschule. Geschichte – aktuelle Entwicklungen – Perspektiven. Bad Heilbrunn: Julius Klinkhardt, 120-132.

⁵ Klafki, W. (1992): Allgemeinbildung in der Grundschule und der Bildungsauftrag des Sachunterrichts. In R. Lauterbach, W. Köhnlein, K. Spreckelsen & E. Klewitz (Hrsg.): Brennpunkte des Sachunterrichts. Kiel: IPN, 11-31.

⁶ Eberwein, H. & Knauer, S. (1998): Handbuch Lernprozesse verstehen. Wege einer neuen (sonder-) pädagogischen Diagnostik. Weinheim: Beltz.

⁷ Miller, S. & Schroeder, R. (2019): Das begrenzte Bildungsverständnis der Hilfsschule. In: Zeitschrift für Grundschulforschung 12 (2), 327-342.

⁸ Werning, R. (1996): Anmerkungen zu einer Didaktik des gemeinsamen Unterrichts. In: Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik 47 (11), 463-469.

⁹ Götz, M., Miller, S., Einsiedler, W. & Vogt, M. (2019): Diskussionspapier zum Selbstverständnis der Grundschulpädagogik als wissenschaftliche Disziplin. In: C. Donie, F. Foerster, M. Obermayr, A. Deckwerth, G.

solves certain individual and collective educational problems, the pedagogical solution of which is disciplined and controlled by professional activity specific to primary school. Accordingly, when they call for the development of their own theory of mass education, they emphasize that for each (author's italics) member of the world and assert that it consists in determining the fundamental methods of self-knowledge. The ideas presented are based on the leading idea of the initial pedagogy of primary education and clearly state that the following theory is associated with a claim directed at all children without any differences¹⁰. In general, no group of children is divided into those who need support or even into those who need special education and those who do not. In the basic educational sense, such an educational need overcomes all restrictions, the symbolism of restoration, the creation of differences through diagnosis and understanding the linear diagnostic-motivational training of special education. From this perspective, the image of the ability of primary school pedagogy to connect with the discourse of inclusion is reversed, since the pedagogy of inclusion is linked to the pedagogy of primary schools, for example, when it comes to Klafka's pedagogical theory or critical constructive didactics. Walken, as a well-known researcher of inclusion, also advocates for an understanding of general education in an inclusive sense as basic education in primary school pedagogy. "Basic education" is a strictly defined technical term that can be applied to the use of inclusive pedagogy as.

Conclusion

Using the example of the guiding principle of basic education, which occupies a central place in the pedagogy of primary schools, an attempt was made to continue the previous changes in the profession and discipline, which were revived as a success story in terms of identity enhancement. At this point, the school, which occupies a central place in the current educational debate, has established academic independence in the field of inclusion. In addition to theoretical work, there are also research questions that need to be answered empirically in order to achieve a primary school-specific understanding of the profession and discipline in this regard. In particular, it is possible to study the teachers' understanding of their tasks and roles in an inclusive environment, which has already been comprehensively studied from the perspective of special education. Researchers' studies show that today, based on the need for comprehensive support for primary education and the need for counseling for school teachers, the use of primary education in developed countries and in general schools is an effective way to implement it in the education system.

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